

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 2.5

Copyright Chart Model

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Project co-ordinator name, Title and Organisation:	Simonetta Buttò, Director of the Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of the Italian Libraries (ICCU)
Tel:	+39 06 49210425
E-mail:	simonetta.butto@beniculturali.it
Project website address:	http://indices-culture.eu/

Author:

Francisco Duque Lima

KU Leuven Centre for IT&IP Law (CiTiP)

Ariadna Matas

Europeana Foundation

Kristina Petrasova

Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Contributing partners:

Maria Drabczyk, Centrum Cyfrowe

Nadia Nadesan, Platoniq

Arina Gorbatyuk, KU Leuven Centre for IT&IP Law (CiTiP)

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the work lead by WP2 and developed in collaboration with multiple WPs to develop a model for an informational tool denominated as the “Copyright Chart”. The process of designing the tool, refining user specifications, selecting content, and outlining relevant information is described in detail.

The current implementation of the Copyright Chart can be found at https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes_groups/4.

2 Introduction and Objectives

This document depicts the development process for the inDICES Copyright Chart, currently implemented as a set of Participatory Processes in the inDICES Portal, accessible to the public.

The main goals of the present document are to shed light on the ubiquity of the results produced by Project inDICES, while directing attention to flawed implementations of ambitions that may have occurred. By thoroughly documenting the process of engaging in such venture, someone interested in the development of similar tools or iterations of the present tool are allowed to conceptualize the steps necessary to do so, and access the necessary content, literature, case-studies, and discussions that permeated the process.

The structure of Deliverable 2.5 is linear, documenting the conceptual approach to copyright capacity building, the core challenges, and the solutions found for the creation of this tool first, the technical choices associated with accessibility and sustainability of the tool in second, and finally, compiling the knowledge base and content in the final section. The structure of the Deliverable follows the same narrative as the process of creating the Copyright Chart: from concept to idea (design), to project (integration), to tool (content).

3 Designing the Copyright Chart

3.1 Concept, challenges and envisioned outcomes

The inDICEs project has consistently strived to generate a multitude of resources to empower not only policy-makers, but any stakeholder aligned with the Project objectives, or integrated into Cultural and Creative Industries (CCI). Some of the core clusters of the project focused on the regulatory framework that influences decision-making processes and the general activity of Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) in the European Union. Amongst all the rules and regulations that affect the role of CHIs in the Digital Single Market, copyright laws can be perceived as some of the most empowering when correctly used, and astringent when incorrectly managed.

Indeed, navigating such a vast ocean of licensing modalities, exceptions, limitations and carveouts may prove challenging to the most experienced. It is, therefore, not to any surprise, that one of the Project's ambitions from the early start has been to find a way to mitigate the inherent discombobulation that complex sets of normative layering bring to the cultural sector.

The goal was, therefore, simple – the plan, not so much: while the core outcome is to provide Cultural Heritage professionals with training and information, the multitude of different ways in which this can be achieved may prove challenging due to what can be described as a readability-granularity dichotomy.

On the one side, regardless of the level of experience of the intended audience (described in section 3.2), the rule of thumb is that the longer and more extensive a resource is, the less time will be spent on it, making it less likely to satisfy the needs of the user. On the other side, the smaller and more “digestible” the resource, the less granular. It seems the problem unfolds in two directions: extensive resources contain most (possibly, all) the necessary information to solve the user's problem or respond to their query, but the user is less likely to reach such content; summarised resources contain a fraction of the necessary information, but the user is more likely to thoroughly engage with it.

Throughout the project's lifecycle, many capacity-building efforts and materials were taken and produced, and all of them can be said to fall on the deeper end of this readable-to-granular spectrum: WP2 produced four extensive deliverables containing high quality academic output about copyright law in the European Union, covering every Directive in the established European copyright acquis, every exception, limitation, and relevant provision for the activities of CHIs. Albeit containing crucial information, such reports span over 100 pages each. Conversely, WP2 presented several conference presentations, online talks and in-person workshops, each of them constrained by time-limits or scoping limits on specific subject matter.

It is therefore evident that the answer lies in the middle: balance had to be struck, and reflected on the design of the final project tool. In order to develop a resource that contained information that is relevant to whomever may be consulting it, two essential clusters needed clearance: correctly defining the target audience and user base in order to cater information to them and, subsequently, filtering

information to suppress details that, albeit crucial in the general scope of copyright knowledge, take a secondary place in the needs of the core audience.

3.2 Intended audience.

However simple it may seem, the intended audience of the copyright tool had to be the same audience that would be interested in accessing inDICEs Project Results. The problem arises when one realises that this audience is extremely broad, spanning from cultural sector professionals, to researchers, to users, artists, creators, curators, among many, many others.

The perspective taken to formulate a generalized user group was that of formulating a broad cluster, denominated “cultural sector professionals”, and identifying different (even if colliding) informational and training needs, amalgamating them into a collective need for professionals in the cultural sector who may be interested in a digital transformation.

The “digital transformation” point is the cornerstone of the conceived intended audience, as the core objectives of Project inDICEs are to empower stakeholders to confidently promote digitization and reuse, two core activities involved in a complete digital transformation. Accordingly, at this point it was also made clear that these resources needed to be organized in a way that makes them accessible to users in any stage *or position* of a digital transformation: granted, they could be staff from a CHI looking to learn about copyright clearance, or the new exceptions for Preservation of Cultural Heritage contained in the DSM Directive, and such staff could be in any level of their digital transformation process: they may be considering to negotiate with external contractors to access infrastructure that may allow them to digitize works, or they may have their set of already digitized archives that they seek to publish online. But one could also consider an artist wanting to publish their work digitally in an open way, or wanting to use another artist’s work, without knowing what kind of permissions they should seek.

This “digital transformation” is polycentric, and holds no formal boundaries: anyone engaging with culture in the digital space, wishing to make it (more) accessible, directly, or indirectly, is part of the broader digital transformation that lies upon us.

WP2 Consultations allowed participating partners to express their perspectives on relevant issues for the broadly-defined “cultural sector professional” audience. In these sessions, various personas from prior Tasks in the project were reintroduced in order to formulate and identify the collective needs of the hypothetical audience.

At this stage, it became evident that the Project workflow had allowed for the construction of crucial resources in the drafting of a core audience.

At the beginning of the inDICEs project, the design for a Model for Community Participation had occurred. In this session, several “personas”¹ involved in the Cultural and Creative Industries were created: Researchers, CHI Practitioners, Policy-Makers... Over 11 case-studies with scenarios, infused with the needs from the sector, allowed a facilitated comprehension of the crucial pain points to be

¹Available on: <https://participate.indices-culture.eu/processes/communityparticipation/f/62/>

addressed in a copyright training resource. The questions and interests of these user groups, as well as particular (and precious) feedback from the Europeana Copyright Office Hours were compiled and imbued with pieces of knowledge stemming from prior Project resources. Another one of those resources worth pointing out is the original copyright-related questionnaire in the first iteration of the Self-Assessment Tool. Extracting context from the multi-layered approach to copyright-related issues in an institution's digital transformation assessment would allow to compare priorities with those compiled insofar.

3.3 Core knowledge base.

From the process highlighted in the prior section, it was then evident that the potential user, interested in making use of the Copyright Tool (Copyright Chart, Copyright Booklet, Copyright Guide, etc...), would mainly be interested in: guidance on strategic approach to digital transformation; information on acquisition, documentation and enrichment (metadata); information on copyright subsistence (authorship, ownership, acquisition); information on copyright exceptions, limitations, flexibilities and carveouts (exceptions from EU legislation and guidance on how to locate them in their National framework, and how these can be used); information on licensing modalities, open licensing and publishing; resources related to these core points; content on re-use and other non-harmonized EU copyright issues.

All these issues were then divided into five clusters, herein denominated the "Core Points":

- 1 - Intellectual Property Strategy*
- 2 - Building Your Collection*
- 3 - Mapping out Copyright Framework in Your Collection*
- 4 - Relying on Copyright to Enable Intended Uses*
- 5 - Fostering Creative Reuse of Your Collection*

Having defined the scope and designed the approach to this public copyright capacity building tool, the next stages comprised defining how it would be published, assessing all relevant considerations about sustainability and accessibility, and which content was most relevant to include under each of these Core Points.

4 Web integration: Participatory Platform

4.1 Preliminary considerations.

The earlier design of the copyright tool envisioned total integration with the inDICES self-assessment tool (SAT). Concerns about the project's lifecycle, the sustainability of a web-based interactive tool, and the difficulty to keep it updated were deemed barriers too stringent to overcome. The tool was adjudicated as an external resource, since, although it most certainly fits the scope of the self-assessment tool (general questionnaire about all aspects related to the digital transformation), it would contribute to its already lengthy extension. Furthermore, copyright issues hold particular independent relevance, if an institution procures knowledge about specific topics related to exploitation of works in their collection, licensing practices, or legal modalities of creative and non-creative reuse.

As such, the Copyright Chart took its independent course, and was set to preliminarily follow the same integration formula as the SAT: questionnaire responses would yield particular grading according to the level of immersion of an institution in their own digital transformation, according to copyright capacity.

In truth, copyright knowledge is not directly and linearly tied to stages of progression in the digital transformation: an institution might be interested in information about digitization and about licensing as parallel processes of the management cycle, and not as stages of a process. As mentioned before, stakeholders engaged in the Cultural and Creative Industries transcend the cluster of "Institutions" too.

In its final iteration, the "Copyright Chart" was reconceptualized as a resource and information hub, not dissimilar to a booklet or guide, implemented and accessible online to those seeking information about specific topics related to copyright.

4.2 Using the Participatory Platform and Processes.

Having defined the means and medium that the Copyright Chart would be brought to life through and from, the choice of implementation in the Participatory Platform follows a triple-tiered logic: in the first layer, the tool should not only subsist as long as possible, be searchable and accessible through adapted reading devices (accessibility), but also editable; secondly, the tool should sustain itself after the Project's lifecycle, and remain accessible to the public; thirdly, the tool could serve a double function as an information hub and a discussion hub.

The inDICEs Participatory Platform was designed with the intention of allowing stakeholders to gather and interact with other members of the industry, so the choice to integrate the Copyright Chart followed naturally.

The tool can be found on this platform, in the form of processes (one for each core point), allowing for follow-up queries, connected proposals, and iterations. As the website describes it, “A participatory process is a sequence of participatory activities (e.g. first filling out a survey, then making proposals, discussing them in face-to-face or virtual meetings, and finally prioritizing them) with the aim of defining and making a decision on a specific topic.”. The idea that static resources could drive dynamic discussion, information, gathering and decision-making connects with all the aforementioned needs, as well as the Project’s objectives.

5 Materials for legal capacity-building

5.1 Scope and usability.

The final step of the process is the compilation of Project resources and information into a quasi-infographic structure. Transcribed below is a compilation of the initial knowledge substrate that gave origin to the current iteration of the Copyright Chart. Segments from different inDICES Deliverables, as well as external resources were compiled into 6 paragraphs per “core point”. The essential ideas were then extracted from this compilation, and organized into smaller, readable, but detailed segments that were used as the final text now present on the Copyright Chart. As a general assessment metric, the summarised version of the compiled knowledge base for each core point should be no longer than 500 words, and have a readability score of at least 50 in the Flesch-Kincaid reading ease test.

5.2 Graphical layout.

The page for each of the distinct “core points” was complemented with illustrations in order to increase readability and comprehension, effectively approximating it to the type of content not dissimilar to a booklet or infographic. While, as explained before, the resource is currently available as a set of Processes on the inDICES Participatory Platform, this layout would allow the information therein contained to be reformulated into a poster, or physical distribution materials such as leaflets.

Figure 1 - Illustration for Core Point 1, Intellectual Property Strategy

5.3 Compiled knowledge base.

5.3.1 Intellectual Property Strategy.

As cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) plan their digital strategy, they must recognize that the issue of copyright management is of paramount importance. Intellectual property rights underlie the works in their collections, and therefore, they can significantly impact the future use of these works, including the manner in which they are accessed, used, and shared. Consequently, CHIs must ensure that they consider copyright management at every step of the way, with the aim of developing a comprehensive strategy that aligns with their goals and objectives.

The copyright landscape is complex, particularly for CHIs that are not the original rightsholders of the works in their collections. As such, they must think proactively about what they want to do with their collections once they have been digitized and determine the rights that they may need to facilitate their intended use. This proactive approach will help them save resources and ensure that they can maximize the impact of their digitized works.

To create a comprehensive digital strategy that takes copyright management into account, CHIs must first understand the legal framework governing copyright. They must be aware of the relevant laws and regulations and be familiar with the terms and conditions of the copyright licenses that they hold. In addition, they must understand how copyright law applies to digital collections, including the implications of fair use, orphan works, and licensing agreements.

Furthermore, CHIs should develop a clear copyright policy that outlines their approach to copyright management, including the measures they will take to ensure compliance with relevant laws and regulations. This policy should provide guidance on issues such as copyright ownership, copyright clearance, and the use of copyrighted materials. By having a clear policy in place, CHIs can avoid ambiguity and ensure that all stakeholders understand their approach to copyright management.

It is also important for CHIs to be aware of the various tools and resources available to them to help with copyright management. These may include copyright clearance centres, copyright management software, and licensing databases. By using these tools and resources effectively, CHIs can streamline the copyright management process and reduce the risk of copyright infringement.

In conclusion, developing a comprehensive copyright management strategy is crucial for CHIs as they plan their digital strategy. By taking a proactive approach and considering copyright management at every step of the way, CHIs can ensure that they maximize the impact of their digitized collections while complying with applicable laws and regulations. Additionally, by having a clear policy in place and using available tools and resources effectively, CHIs can streamline the copyright management process and ensure that they are in compliance with relevant laws and regulations.

5.3.2 Building Your Collection.

The acquisition of a physical artwork by a cultural heritage institution (CHI) does not necessarily mean that all the rights required to use and display the artwork have been obtained. The rights underlying the work may be owned by a different person or institution, and it is essential that CHIs understand this before proceeding with any further use or dissemination of the work. To ensure that the necessary rights have been obtained, CHIs must have explicit agreements in place with the person or institution holding these rights.

Once a CHI acquires a work, it presents a prime opportunity to contact the rightsholder to ensure that the necessary permissions have been obtained. By doing so, CHIs can ensure that they are in compliance with the legal framework governing intellectual property rights (IPRs) and prevent any legal complications in the future.

When obtaining rights to use a work, CHIs must ensure that the contracts they rely on clearly state the scope of the rights being obtained. For instance, if a CHI intends to display the work in an exhibition or online repository, it must obtain permission to do so explicitly. This proactive approach can save CHIs from going through extra layers of clearance in the future.

Moreover, CHIs must accurately document the rights they have obtained, the duration, and any conditions or requirements attached to them. This documentation can help ensure transparency and facilitate the use of the works across the organization and in the long run.

In addition to documentation, CHIs must retrieve and record as much metadata as possible. For instance, information about the author, date of creation, and date of publication can be helpful in facilitating future use and circulation of the work. This information may be difficult to obtain later, and therefore, it is essential to obtain it during the acquisition process.

In conclusion, CHIs must be proactive in obtaining the necessary rights to use works in their collections. This requires clear and explicit agreements with the person or institution holding the rights, accurate documentation of the rights obtained, and the retrieval and recording of as much metadata as possible. By following these steps, CHIs can ensure that they are in compliance with the legal framework governing IPRs and avoid any legal complications in the future.

5.3.3 Mapping out Copyright Framework in Your Collection.

Cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) must obtain the necessary rights before digitizing their collections and making them available to the public. However, obtaining these rights can be a complex and costly process. CHIs often enter into licensing agreements with rightsholders to obtain the required authorization to make certain uses of the works.

When considering the use of a work in a collection, it is essential to determine whether the work is in the public domain. If the copyright has expired or was never granted, the work can be used without the need for permission, although moral rights may still apply.

If the work is still under copyright, and CHIs have not obtained the necessary rights during the acquisition phase, they must seek permission from the rightsholder through a licensing agreement. Rightsholders are entitled to receive proper remuneration for the use of their work by third parties, and licensing agreements provide a means of obtaining the necessary permissions while compensating the rightsholder.

There are also exceptions and limitations to copyright law that apply to specific categories of users and uses, and these can be explored to determine whether permission from the rightsholder is necessary. If the work is still under copyright, and no exception applies, CHIs must identify the author or the collective management organization (CMO) that operates on their behalf to obtain the necessary permissions.

To develop a successful copyright strategy, CHIs must establish good communication with rightsholders and define their long-term goals early on. The copyright strategy must align with the intended use of the collection, and CHIs must ensure that the necessary permissions are obtained before making the works available to the public.

In conclusion, obtaining the necessary permissions to use works in a CHI's collection can be a complicated and costly process. CHIs must explore all available options to determine whether permission from the rightsholder is necessary and establish good communication with them. By developing a clear copyright strategy that aligns with their long-term goals, CHIs can ensure that their collections are used in compliance with the applicable laws and regulations, while at the same time, maximizing their impact.

5.3.4 Relying on Copyright to Enable Intended Uses.

Cultural institutions play a vital role in fulfilling their public mission by providing access to works through various means such as exhibitions, access to printed or digitized material, and welcoming the general public to the premises of the institution. However, these activities may require permission from the copyright owner, unless an exception to copyright exists. When it comes to preservation, CHIs must check their national legislation for a preservation copyright exception. They should pay particular attention to their national definition of C-1 "preservation purposes" and the scope of the exception. They must determine if it is restricted to works permanently in their collection and whether all permitted uses are limited to essential acts of preservation.

Making copies of works to advertise an exhibition can be done without specific permission from the rightsholder in jurisdictions that have implemented this exception. Digital advertising, such as any online advertising or catalogue for the exhibition, is generally covered by this exception.

Giving online access to the public can be a complex matter, as there is no general exception at the EU level that allows CHIs to freely share their collections online. However, there are exceptions for specific categories of works. CHIs can ascertain whether the work is an orphan or out-of-commerce work, and if it falls in one of the permitted categories of works, they may use it without permission. In the case of the latter, they will need to acquire a license from a representative CMO (if one exists), or they may share the work online without permission.

When supporting research activities, CHIs may provide access to their collections by relying on an exception. They can also allow access to works for research and private study purposes when carried out via dedicated terminals in their institution (this exception is still subject to variations in national legislation).

In conclusion, cultural institutions must be aware of the applicable copyright laws and regulations when providing access to works in their collections. They must determine whether an exception to copyright exists or whether they need to obtain permission from the copyright owner. By being aware of these regulations and exceptions, CHIs can continue to fulfil their public mission while staying in compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

5.3.5 Fostering Creative Reuse of Your Collection.

Cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) are increasingly seeking new ways to interact with their audience, raise awareness of their collections, and facilitate equal access to cultural heritage for all citizens. Alongside preserving and giving access to their digital cultural heritage, CHIs may want to take steps to encourage and facilitate its use to maximize its impact on society. To do so, CHIs must first consider for which purposes they want to provide re-use of their collections, such as research, education, or commercial purposes, and take some considerations into account.

One of the critical considerations is to communicate the copyright status of the collection in a clear manner. Adhering to standards, rights statements or Creative Commons (CC) licenses can maximize the potential for the re-use of a collection. CC licenses, such as the simple attribution [BY] and share-alike [BY-SA] licenses, and tools, like the CCO copyright waiver, are some of the simplest means to convey what can be made with the digital cultural heritage assets and to foster their re-use and circulation.

Another crucial consideration is to rely on licensing metadata standards to help users find the work and bolster its reusability. By using these standards, CHIs can provide users with information about the rights that apply to a work and how it can be used.

Additionally, the Europeana Publishing Framework is a useful resource that can help CHIs learn how to best manage the metadata in their cultural assets. It provides guidance on creating descriptive metadata, using controlled vocabularies, and assigning rights statements, among other things.

Lastly, it is essential to remember that, regardless of the copyright strategy, exceptions or licenses that may have been acquired, the author's moral rights still subsist. Enabling re-use of a work does not necessarily enable any use, and CHIs must respect the author's moral rights, including the right to be attributed and the right to object to derogatory treatment.

In conclusion, CHIs must take specific considerations into account when facilitating the re-use of their digital cultural heritage. By communicating the copyright status of their collections, using licensing metadata standards, and adhering to best practices and guidelines, CHIs can maximize the potential for re-use and circulation of their collections while respecting the author's moral rights. By doing so,

they can promote equal access to cultural heritage for all citizens and enhance the impact of their collections on society.

6 Conclusions

The development process for the Copyright Chart model was documented based on what can be considered the three crucial stages of its creation. Its design, ultimately a task made to counter the heaviness and extensiveness of materials about copyright that were produced in a more academic fashion. Its implementation, or, as described, the choice to keep it as a static tool in an Online Platform, motivated by considerations on sustainability and accessibility, as well as ease of use. And, of course, its content, what is considered useful for the predefined user base, and how can it be presented in a way that is useful for them.

On the one hand, all the fundamental Project resources, takeaways, and conclusions from prior work were crucial to correctly define the scope, design, and approach to such a tool. Without those resources, the multitude of branching pathways and options to be chose from when designing such a resource would be impossible to sift through. On the other hand, it is also true that such a tool would benefit from a longer design cycle that would follow the knowledge created in the project as it comes to life.

Currently, the Copyright Chart is implemented and integrated as a public resource that, as aforementioned, serves a double function of attracting stakeholders to a discussion space designed for community engagement. The perks of this double function cannot be overlooked: ideally, if correctly , the current iteration of the tool's design would allow not only for the clarification , but for subsequential discussion hubs about the issues, fostering community participation, collective knowledge, and empowering stakeholders in their venture into the digital transformation.